

Dual-Responsive Gradient Structured Actuator via Photopolymerization-Induced Diffusion

Duygu Sezen Polat,^[a] Vera E. Buurman,^[a] Dirk J. Mulder,^[b] and Danqing Liu*^[a]

Stimuli-responsive materials have recently gained significant attention in the field of soft robotics, sensors, and biomimetic devices. The most facile way for the fabrication of such materials remains to endow bilayer structures which are fabricated with the combination of active and passive layers. Although, easily fabricated, these structures suffer from the generation of stress points between connection areas. In this work we develop a method to create a thin film with controlled cross-link variation across its thickness. The cross-link gradient is achieved through polymerization induced diffusion of dithiol

molecules in thiol-ene network. As a result, the film exhibits bending deformation upon illumination with light or exposure to a chemical solvent, thereby demonstrating dual responsiveness. Light actuation of the film is achieved via photothermal effects due to the incorporation of dye into the system which can absorb UV light and heat the network. While solvent induced actuation is due to anisotropic swelling. Furthermore, the straightforward fabrication procedure allows for the creation of more complex deformations by patterning the film using a photomask during photopolymerization.

Introduction

Nature is a constant source of inspiration for scientists designing responsive materials, which make it possible to develop walking polymers inspired by worms,^[1,2] grippers inspired by pythons^[3] and robots that move like human arms.^[4] Elegant machineries of nature are highly functional and efficient in their responsiveness to changing environments through exhibiting complex and diverse deformations. Such intricate motions arise from the anisotropic variations in their gradient structures. Sea cucumbers, for instance, adeptly regulate their dermal stiffness for survival,^[5] while carrotwood seed pods employ their porous gradient structure to safeguard seeds in challenging, varying humidity conditions.^[6]

Gradient structured actuators respond to various external stimuli such as temperature,^[7–9] chemicals,^[10,11] humidity,^[12,13] light^[14] and pH^[15,16] to achieve complex deformations without the risk of delamination commonly observed in bilayer systems due to stress concentrations at contact zones.^[17] Gradient structured actuators can also offer enhanced control, robust-

ness and flexibility due to continuous changes in their physical properties.^[18] Previously gradient structured actuators have been fabricated from hydrogels,^[8,15,19–21] shape memory polymers,^[22,23] graphene oxide membranes^[24] and liquid crystal elastomers (LCEs).^[25–28]

In this work, we present a straightforward method for the fabrication of a gradient structured actuator with high cross-link density regions for strength and dimensional stability, and low cross-link density regions for compliance and elastic behavior. To achieve this, we employ two distinct photoinitiator systems that can selectively polymerize thiol-ene polymerization and acrylate homopolymerization. Our aim is to fabricate the network with changing cross-link density across its thickness, accomplished by polymerization-induced diffusion of dithiol molecules during thiol-ene step-growth polymerization. This structure is then fixed by acrylate homopolymerization. As thiol-ene network is softer than acrylate network, the resulting film exhibits a gradient in modulus along its thickness which leads to macroscopic bending of the film upon actuation. In air, upon illumination with light, the film bends due to asymmetric expansion and in solvent due to asymmetric swelling. This mechanical deformation is controlled by photopolymerization conditions. Building upon this foundation, we further advanced the system to fabricate a more complex structure. Utilizing lithographic method, we alter the direction of the cross-link density gradient along the thickness direction, achieving wave-like motion. Our method offers a general strategy for the fabrication of gradient structured actuators.

Results and Discussion

We fabricated our gradient structured films using a two-step photopolymerization process. Figure 1A illustrates the chemical structures of the compounds. Monomers **1** and **2** are liquid crystal diacrylate monomers and dithiol **3** acts as a chain

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Figure 1. A. Chemical structures of the compounds used for the fabrication of thiol-ene based network with cross-link density gradient. B. UV-vis spectra of the photo initiators and photoabsorbent dye. C. Schematic representation of the fabrication procedure.

extender. We used photoinitiator systems 4 and 5, which unlike Irgacure 819 can selectively initiate thiol-ene polymerization and acrylate homopolymerization, respectively.^[29] Photoinitiator 4 is a Type I photoinitiator which initiates the step-growth thiol-ene reaction. Photoinitiator system 5 consists of Type II photoinitiator that initiates chain-growth acrylate homopolymerization and coinitiator which stabilizes the radicals generated by the photoinitiator and increases its efficiency.^[30] We added photoabsorbent dye 6 which absorbs light at the same wavelength as photoinitiator 4 to create a light gradient throughout the thickness of the sample.

In a typical experiment, we fabricated gradient structured actuator by incorporating 15 mol% 3, 1:1 ratio of monomers 1 and 2. We melted a small quantity (70 mg) of reaction mixture in a polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) coated glass cell with spacers to ensure a controlled and uniform film thickness. During the first step, we illuminated the sample with 365 nm light which is absorbed by photoinitiator 4. When initiated, 4 generates two relatively stable lophyl radicals which can abstract hydrogen from thiol molecules to produce thiyl radicals.^[31] Radical-mediated thiol-ene polymerization reaction can then take place.^[29,32] To generate the formation of cross-link density gradient, we investigated whether we could achieve concentration gradient of dithiol molecules in the network during photopolymerization through diffusion. To achieve this, we added a small amount (1.6 mol%) of UV absorbing dye, 6, with an absorption maximum (Figure 1B) close to the photoinitiator, 4, which creates a light intensity gradient over the thickness of the sample (Figure S1).^[33,34] Therefore, reaction rate is faster at the lamp side of the film (LD), thus leading to a faster consumption of dithiols. Dithiol depletion can then drive the diffusion process leading LD to be enriched with dithiol, and the other side (HD) with diacrylate monomers (Figure 1C). We expect mainly dithiol 3 molecule to diffuse due to its small size which is known to facilitate diffusion.^[35] In this step, we chose

to illuminate the sample with a relatively low light intensity at 0.05 mW/cm² for 83 minutes to further facilitate the diffusion. In the second step, we illuminated the sample with 455 nm light which is absorbed by the 5 (Figure 1B). Upon illumination with visible light, 5 initiates the chain-growth acrylate homopolymerization reaction and arrests the spatial gradient of cross-link density.^[29,36] We illuminated the sample with a light intensity of 18 mW/cm² for 10 minutes at 60 °C, above its T_{Ni} (Figure S2). We characterized the conversion of photopolymerization with Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) by examining the =CH₂ twisting vibration peak at 810 cm⁻¹ (Figure S3).^[26] We performed kinetic studies for thiol-ene polymerization and acrylate homopolymerization while illuminating the sample with 365 nm and 455 nm light, respectively. 92% of total conversion can be observed after these two steps (Figure 2A and Figure 2B). To reduce the stresses caused by photopolymerization, we then post-baked the film at 120 °C for 20 min.^[1] To confirm the polymerization induced diffusion of 3 through the network, we performed Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) analysis which revealed a 13.0% difference for S content between HD and LD higher at the LD which can be seen in Figure 2C and Figure S4. We also observed that C content is 6.9% higher in HD-side.

Next, we investigated the influence of the composition, illustrated in Figure 1A on the mechanical properties of the polymer film. For this purpose, film with dimensions of 14 mm×2 mm was clamped from one end and illuminated with 365 nm light from HD, which can be absorbed by photothermal dye 6 and heat the network. Figure 2D shows the mechanical deformation of the film upon illumination with light. For a polydomain network (Figure S5), heating would cause expansion in all directions. However, we observed that the film always bends toward HD upon illumination exhibiting macroscopic deformation. As the film does not have any molecular alignment, this actuation hints that indeed HD and LD have different

Figure 2. A. Conversion of acrylate functional groups during illumination with 365 nm. B. Conversion of acrylate functional groups during illumination with 455 nm. C. Corresponding EDX analysis results analysis result for HD and LD. D. Photothermal actuation of the film upon illumination with 365 nm light. E. Illustration of the bending deformation of the cross-link gradient network. F. Swelling induced bending deformation of the film in toluene bath. Scale bars correspond to 4 mm.

mechanical properties. As the LD has lower network density, and thus expand easier. While in case of HD, the thermal expansion is suppressed due to greater cross-link density. This asymmetric thermal expansion results in a bending deformation (Figure 2E). The bending angle of the film increases at a higher rate above 46.9 °C which could be explained by heating the network above its T_g which is around 49.7 °C (Figure S6). At 82.4 °C, film was able to achieve a bending angle of 27°.

Beside light responsiveness, we also investigated solvent responsiveness of the polymer networks, by swelling the film in toluene. Film (14 mm×2 mm) was clamped from one end and immersed into a toluene bath. Figure 2F shows the deformation behavior of the film during swelling. Film curls towards the HD reaching a maximum curvature of 0.5 mm⁻¹ in 44 minutes. Since swelling is a diffusion determined process, toluene molecules can diffuse into the network faster from the LD which leads to the formation of tightly curled film due to the differences in the absorption kinetics. After 44 minutes, the curvature of the film starts to decrease, equilibrating after 108 minutes at curvature of 0.14 mm⁻¹. This is because when given more time, toluene molecules can also diffuse to the densely cross-linked HD and film starts losing curvature.

Having established the polymer network with cross-link gradient, we further investigated the influence of diffusion kinetics on the mechanical deformation of the polymer films. We tested three chain extender concentrations of 10 mol%, 15 mol% and 20 mol%. We also tested three different illumination conditions: 1 mW/cm² for 250 seconds, 0.5 mW/cm² for 500

seconds and 0.05 mW/cm² for 5000 seconds. Illumination conditions were set such that the total exposure was 250 mJ/cm². Results of this study can be seen in Figure 3A–C. Increasing light intensity during photopolymerization decreased the maximum bending angle of all the films. This phenomenon can be attributed to the accelerated polymerization process, leading to increased viscosity that restricts the diffusion of dithiol molecules. Moreover, an elevated illumination intensity increases UV light penetration, causing thiol-acrylate reactions to occur at a larger depth, decreasing the concentration gradient across the thickness. This, in turn, diminishes the cross-link difference leading to less mechanical deformation.

Increasing the chain extender concentration, and therefore also the cross-link density, results in a change of mechanical properties such as storage modulus and T_g . The bulk storage modulus at 30 °C decreases from 3.6 GPa with 10 mol% dithiol, to 2.4 GPa with 15 mol% dithiol, and finally to 0.6 GPa for mixtures with 20 mol% **3** (Figure S7). Film containing 20 mol% dithiol exhibited the greatest deformation, achieving a maximum bending angle of 43° at 82 °C. This aligns with the anticipated behavior, as softer materials typically offer less resistance to deformation. Polymerization induced diffusion can also be changed by altering the concentration of **6** as it affects the penetration depth of 365 nm light during the first step of photopolymerization. We prepared polymer networks with dye concentrations of 1.6 mol% and 2.2 mol%. We increased the total exposure to 37.5% accounting for the light absorbed by **6**. Difference in the mechanical properties of HD and LD of this

Figure 3. Photothermal bending of gradient structured films. Investigation of the influence of light intensity during the first step of photopolymerization for the films fabricated with (A) 10 mol%, (B) 15 mol% and (C) 20 mol% dithiol concentration. D. Influence of light intensity during the first step of photopolymerization for the films fabricated with 2.2 mol% photoabsorbent dye. E. Stacked image of the film fabricated with 2.2 mol% photoabsorbent dye at 0.05 mW/cm² light intensity during photothermal actuation. Scale bar corresponds to 2 mm. F. Corresponding EDX analysis result for HD and LD.

film was observed to be the largest which can be seen in Figure 3D and 3E. As can be seen from Figure 3F and Figure S8, increasing dye concentration led to 26% difference between HD and LD for S atom%, which could explain the improved mechanical deformation.

We also observed a similar trend for the swelling performance of the films. Increasing dithiol concentration and decreasing light intensity during the first step of photopolymerization improves the swelling kinetics of the films and increases the maximum curvature that they can achieve as can be seen in Figure 4. Film with 5 mol% **3** concentrations only achieved a maximum curvature of 0.05 mm⁻¹ after 50 minutes. The film

with 15 mol% on the other hand achieved a maximum curvature of 1.18 mm⁻¹ in 14 minutes. The film was able to maintain this curvature for 12 minutes. Film fabricated with same concentration of **3** with higher light intensity in the first step achieved a maximum curvature of 0.65 mm⁻¹. However, kinetics were significantly slower, taking 100 minutes to achieve this curvature.

Moreover, to understand the influence of the thickness on the extent of diffusion, we prepared samples with different thicknesses in the range of 10 μm to 200 μm and investigated their photothermal actuation (Figure S8). Film with 10 μm exhibited very little bending deformation which could be

Figure 4. Swelling induced bending deformation of gradient structured films A. Stacked images of the films fabricated with different dithiol concentrations and light intensities during the first of photopolymerization in toluene bath during swelling. Scale bars correspond to 2 mm. B. Corresponding swelling kinetics of the films.

explained by its comparable dimension to the penetration depth of 7.55 μm (Figure S1). Similarly, film with 200 μm thickness also exhibited very little bending deformation since the diffusion does not take place through the entire thickness. As a result, we observe a trend that hints an optimum for the gradient structure and film with a thickness of 40 μm can achieve a maximum bending angle of 75°.

Another photopolymerization parameter that we altered was the temperature as increasing temperature can reduce viscosity of the reaction mixture and enhance species mobility, promoting the diffusion of **3**. A risk of increasing the temperature, however, is the occurrence of premature polymerization which would increase the viscosity, thereby hindering the diffusion of **3** to the surface. Therefore, we did not observe a significant influence of photopolymerization temperature in the experimentally viable range (Figure S9).

As functional actuators, reversible and recoverable actuation is critical for practical applications. Given in Figure S10 film achieved a maximum bending angle of 62° upon illumination with 365 nm light. After turning off the light, the film rapidly uncurls to a bending angle of 27°. There are two distinct mechanisms that can explain this irreversible deformation. First, when the films are polymerized in the cell setup, polymer shrinkage will be more prevalent on HD.^[37] During the first heating round, there will be stress relaxation, causing for a bend in the material towards HD. Second, whenever the sample reaches for temperatures comparable to T_g for the first time,

there is an irreversible change in the microstructure of the plastic.^[38] We repeated this cyclic process ten times and observed no discernible reduction in actuation.

Finally, due to the versatile fabrication method we also prepared films that can exhibit more complex deformations. To fabricate patterned networks, we carried out the photopolymerization in three steps. First, we exposed the sample to 365 nm light through a photomask as depicted in Figure 5A. Subsequently, we inverted the sample, and subjected it to 365 nm light, employing a negative photomask during this exposure. We then illuminated the sample with 455 nm light to arrest the cross-link gradient. This strategy allows for generating more complex shape transformations without the need of multiple stimuli or responsive moieties. After the removal from the substrate, we observed different directions of the curvature in different parts of the film. We tested swelling induced bending deformation of this film when immersed in a toluene bath. As depicted in Figure 5B, the strip exhibits a bending pattern resembling that of a “paperclip.” Curvatures of the different parts increase in different directions due to fabrication procedure. At equilibrium the entire film is swollen. As shown in Figure 5C, the film is cut into the shape of a flower with laser cutter. When immersed in a toluene bath, petals of the film start bending toward HD, resulting in the gradual closure of the flower. Artificial flower recovers its initial shape after deswelling.

Figure 5. (A) Schematic representation for the fabrication of patterned networks with alternating cross-link gradient. (B) Swelling induced bending behavior of patterned films. (C) Swelling induced bending behavior of ‘flower’ shaped film. Scale bars correspond to 2 mm.

Conclusions

In this work, we fabricated a dual responsive soft actuator with cross-link gradient. We introduced cross-link gradient through polymerization-induced diffusion of dithiol molecules in a thiol-ene network. Light intensity gradient was created by the addition of a photoabsorbent dye that absorbs the same wavelength of light as the thiol-ene step-growth polymerization photoinitiator. We investigated the influence of photopolymerization conditions on the dual responsiveness of the films. Finally, we fabricated patterned films that were able to undergo more complex deformation modes through photomask exposure. This work demonstrates a versatile fabrication procedure for soft actuators.

Experimental Section

Materials

4-phenylene bis(4-((6-(acryloyloxy)hexyl)oxy)benzoate) (1) and 2-Methyl-1,4-phenylene bis(4-(3-(acryloyloxy)propoxy)benzoate) (2), 2,2'-(Ethylendioxy)diethanethiol (3), 2,2'-bis(2-chlorophenyl)-4,4',5,5'-tetraphenyl-1,1'-biimidazole (4), camphor quinone (5), and ethyl-dimethyl amino benzoate (5), and 2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-di-tert-pentylphenol (6), polyvinyl alcohol (6000 g/mol), dichloromethane (DCM), and toluene. All materials and solvents were purchased commercially without further purification.

Fabrication of Gradient Structured Films

Thiol-ene polymer networks were fabricated by a two-step photopolymerization of the mixture in a cell setup. Clean glass substrates were spin coated with 5 wt.% polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) solution, initializing at 1000 rpm for 5 seconds, followed by 2500 rpm for 30 seconds. Coated substrates were then placed on a hotplate for 30 minutes at 60 °C to evaporate the solvent. Substrate was then placed on a hot plate and 70 mg of the mixture was added on top of it. UV-curable glue with spacers with a diameter of 20 μm were placed on its corners. Another coated substrate was carefully pressed to ensure uniform thickness. Sample was then exposed to 365 nm light (Thorlabs M365 L3-C2) at different illumination conditions which satisfies exposure dose of 250 mJ/cm². Afterwards, the sample was illuminated for 10 minutes with 455 nm light (Thorlabs M455 L3-C2) with an intensity of 18 mW/cm², followed by a post-curing step, carried out for 20 minutes at 120 °C. To facilitate the removal of the film, sample was immersed in a water bath of 60 °C for approximately 2 hours. A razor blade was inserted at one edge, causing the cell to open.

Characterization

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was conducted to measure the chemical structure of the polymers using a Varian 670 IR equipped with a golden gate setup. For the kinetics measurement reaction mixture mixed with spacers was placed on top of the crystal and a glass slide was gently pressed on it to achieve uniform thickness to replicate the photopolymerization conditions. Following the application of a 20 μm thick layer of gold or platinum through a Quorum Q 150T S plus SEM coating system via spin coating, Energy-dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX) was applied along with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) on the JEOL JSM-IT100 or

Phenom Pro X, both operated at 10 kV to analyze the types and the quantity of elements at the two surfaces of the polymer. The phase transition temperatures of monomer mixtures were determined by a Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) on a TA instruments Q1000. Three heating cycles were implemented, involving increments of 5 °C for both heating and cooling. The phase transition temperature of the mixture was determined as the onset temperature on the endotherm during the first heating process, as the mixture underwent thermal polymerization after one heating cycle. The determination of the phase transitions was verified using a Leica DM2700-M polarized optical microscope (POM) equipped with the Linkam heating stage. The assessment of mechanical properties was done using Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) on samples measuring 12 mm×5.3 mm with a thickness of 20 μm. Samples were secured in a TA Instruments DMA Q800 operating in DMA-Multi-Frequency-Strain mode, applying a preload force of 0.0100 mN. The set amplitude was 15.000 μm, and the set frequency was 1 Hz. A temperature ramp from 30 °C to 120 °C was executed at a rate of 3 °C/min.

Analysis of dual responsiveness The as-prepared polymer film was cut into strips of 14 mm ×2 mm and was clamped from one end, while the other end was free to suspend in the air. Subsequently, films were irradiated with a LED (Thorlabs M365 L3-C2) at 365 nm equipped with a collimator. The bending angle, serving as an indicator of mechanical deformation, was tracked using ImageJ at various light intensities. Films were simultaneously monitored with Fluke TIS32 thermal camera. For swelling experiments, films were immersed into toluene bath at room temperature and their deformation behavior was monitored with digital camera. Swelling kinetics were tracked with a custom Blender script.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: gradient structure · bioinspired · swelling · responsive material · polymer

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

A method has been developed for the fabrication of gradient-structured actuators with cross-link variation by using two distinct photoinitiator systems to selectively trigger thiol-ene polymerization and acrylate homopolymerization. The gradient-structured actuator undergoes bending deformation in both air and solvent environments, and can be controlled by carefully tailoring the photopolymerization conditions.

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